

Analysis Factor of Marketing Strategy of Funding Decision of Customers Choose Baitul Mal Wat Tamwil (BMT) In Kolaka Regency, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research was to determine the factors that influence a client's decision in choosing BMT in the Kolaka Regency, Sulawesi Tenggara. Type of research is the study quantitative associative. Tests were carried out, covering Validity and reliabilita, then continued with, test multiple regression analysis using SPSS version 16.0. The results showed Community decision base on calculated rated R square of 0.975 or 95.7% strongly influenced by the factor have been determined, such as product, price, place, and promotion. The value of the constant is 0.026, 0.925 for products, 0.889 for price, 0.654 for place, 1.554 for promotion. then it can be concluded from these data regression equation is: $Y = 0.026 + 0.925X_1 + 0.889X_2 + 0.654X_3 + 1.554X_4$. Concluded that factor marketing strategy of funding decision of customer choose BMT in Kolaka Regency is product, place, and promotion. However, variable price was not significantly.

Keywords: Factor, Marketing, Strategy, Baitul Maal Wat Tamwil (BMT), Kolaka.

Introduction

Islam is a universal religion, all aspects of human life to be attention, so the scholars of Islamic religious formulate in five formula. One of them is the maintenance of treasure, treasure recognized its interest in the religion of Islam, so it is not justified a Muslim take the property of others on the grounds that the property of God, so that the prohibition was a chain of Islamic religion, that inappropriate/chic for a Muslim to seek sustenance by road falsehood. Religion present in the midst of humanity to build civilizations, social, cultural, and economic. Development of economic civilization through Baitul Maal Wat Tamwil (BMT) is a alternative strategy after seeing the pattern of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that could have happened to the people. BMT so that the presence in our midst as the answers that we are the ones who follow the prophet, which is not only filling our own stomachs besides us there are neighbors who are experiencing hunger.

Baitul Maal Wat Tamwil (BMT) as an alternative financial institution is expected to make a significant contribution in the development of the real economy, especially for businesses that do not meet all the requirements to obtain financing from the Islamic banking institutions. The development of the real economy will be able to take place quickly when supported by the availability of adequate financial resources and in accordance with the values of justice (Suhendi, 2009). Lin (2002), states that there are three forms of capital, namely: economic capital, cultural capital and social capital. All three forms of capital are mutually supportive in the operation of all types of financial institutions in general only in conventional financial institutions that stand out is the economic capital. But not so the financial institutions that use the principle of profit / loss sharing or return sharing, especially the use of sharia contract. Enormous contribution of social capital in support of the operational organization and distribution of funds due to limited regions and operational systems in BMT.

Objective Study

BMT development pattern that compete and are not selling well in the community to be a problem that needs to be investigated, namely products

Cooperative Trade Unit, Organization of the financial non-banking or even banking. BMT function that is present in our midst, which aims to develop the economy of small and medium class actually be monitored and evaluated for the convenience and economic civilization of the people. Therefore, researchers are interested to analyze the marketing strategy of financing products to the customer's decision choosing BMT.

Research Question

How to influence the differentiation of product, price, place, promotion to the customer's decision in choosing BMT in Kolaka Regency, Sulawesi Tenggara ?

Significances of Study

The purpose of this research was to determine the factors influence a client's decision in choosing BMT in the Kolaka Regency, Sulawesi Tenggara.

Material and Method

Research Method

Type of research is the study Quantitative associative. Is a research that aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables. Forms of relationships in this study is the relationship clause. Namely a causal relationship arising from product differentiation independent variable (X1), price (X2), point (X3), promotion (X4) to the customer's decision dependent variable (Y).

Conceptual Framework

Source: Damirchi 2003

Population and Sample

Samples BMT research is contained in Kolaka. Research conducted in April 2016.

Sources of Data, Variables and Scales of Measurement

Source of Data

a. Primary data

In this study the data obtained directly by questionnaire or list of questions to customer financing BMT, a total of 20 numbers question.

b. Secondary data

Secondary data in this study was obtained through the annual report, documents such as notes, drawings or photographs.

Variables

a. Variable independent

In this study, the independent variable used is the marketing strategy (variable X), which consists of product, price, place, promotion.

b. Variable dependent

In this study, the dependent variable used is the customer's decision BMT.

Scale of Measurement

In this study, using a Likert scale measurement scale used to measure attitudes, opinions, perceptions of a person or a customer of social phenomena.

Data Analysis

Activities in classifying data based on analysis of data variables and the respondents, tabulate the data based on the variable of all respondents, presenting the data of each variable studied, perform calculations to test the hypothesis that has been done.

Tests were carried out, covering Validity and reliability, then continued with, test multiple regression analysis using SPSS version 16.0

Result and Discussion

Instrument test validity and realibility

Output test the validity of the instrument (data) shows that there are five invalid data can not be used subsequent analysis. From the output reliability test

showed coefficient alpha (α) of all items instrument ≥ 0.60 means all data items (instrument) trustworthy reliability. It can be concluded that the entire item (item) used are reliable therefore, a questionnaire used may be feasible as an instrument to take measurements.

Table. 1 Reliability statistics

Cronbach Alpha	Cronbach Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
3.724	0.848	20

Regression factor of marketing strategy of funding decision of customer choose BMT.

Table. 2 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Costumer Decision	15.4600	1.71023	10
Product	3.5600	0.52324	10
Price	3.9200	0.42374	10
Place	4.1600	0.59479	10
Promotion	3.8200	0.74506	10

Tabel 3. Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R Square	Std. error of estimate	Durbin- watson
1	0.987	0.975	0.954	0.36587	2.534

In the column Durbin-watson 2534 numbers which means there is above +2 which means there is a negative correlation. Values between -2 to +2

(approximately 2 indicating the absence of serial correlation, in this case the data in this study no serial correlation; deviation from this value indicates that the residues randomly distributed.

Table 4. ANOVA

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	25.655	4	6.414	47.912	0.000
Residual	0.669	5	0.134		
Total	26.324	9			

The above results indicate that the significance of the results is 0.0002 or were <0.05 , indicating that the dependent is influenced not happen heterogeneous independent or not different or underestimated because of the same.

The results showed (based on table 5), that the value of the constant is 0.026, 0.925 for products, 0.889 for price, 0.654 for place, 1.554 for promotion. then it can be concluded from these data regression equation is: $Y = 0.026 + 0.925X_1 + 0.889X_2 + 0.654X_3 + 1.554X_4$.

From these equations can be explained that all the regression coefficient is positive, it indicates that the influence of services in line with the community's decision to select / use the product from the BMT contained in Kolaka. This means that if a product, price, place and promotion of improved statistics will encourage community interest in selecting and using BMT in Kolaka. Rated R square of 0.957 or 95.7% of this case showed that the community's decision to use/choose products BMT strongly influenced by the factors that have been determined, such as product, price, place and promotion.

Table 5. Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.026	1.732		0.015	0.989
	Product	0.925	0.237	0.283	3.907	0.011
	Price	0.889	0.447	0.220	1.988	0.104
	Place	0.654	0.228	0.227	2.872	0.035
	Promotion	1.554	0.260	0.677	5.974	0.002

Regression analysis showed that of the four factors of the marketing strategy of financing products to the customer's decision choosing BMT is strongly influenced by significant promotional effect on positive messages ($P < 0.05$). Communication networks, especially in the religious group will facilitate this promotion. Personal communication and in depth will make prospective customers more aware of the financial products BMT. Muljadi *et al.*, (2014), Showed that promotion in BMTS uses brochure and study groups (religious group) as a means to introduce of BMT product. Promotion of BMT product is suitable with the shariah concept. Then, determination of place BMT is still simple. The choice as the place is closed to the mosque, market, school or collage and boarding school. The determination of places BMTS is not a deviation from the shariah concept. Hascaryani *et al.*, (2011), stated that some BMT independent used approach personal method to communities, by value as entry point to the community for funding or sharing, the another time will growth *Ukhuwah* (brotherhood). In this way, facilitate networking BMT to make a positive impact on market expansion BMT. In terms of marketing costs, the existence of networks that have been formed very beneficial for cost savings.

Promotions that will generate interest for customers to choose and use products BMT in Kolaka. Promotion through internet network or on line will allow potential customers to obtain information about the product. Promotions that use Community Leader / Indigenous / Religion as a brand of products that will instill confidence in the product, could even increase with the testimony from these figures. Hosen and Sa'roni (2012), showed that one of the main determinant factor of the BMT success

rate are Information Technology (IT) and Network. Prayitno (2015), showed that the most dominant variable in BMT Tumang Branch Salatiga is variable promotion. Because of their premises sale through distribution of brochures, print media, gifts will have an effect on customer loyalty.

Variable product in this study had a positive effect of about 0.925 was significantly ($P < 0.05$) against the decision of consumers to choose BMT in Kolaka. Various types of products supplied by BMT in Kolaka makes the value of a variable product is quite high compared to some literature. Variations of products makes customers may choose, for their diverse selection with many advantages in the context of sharia, and without prejudice to and aggravating the other. Pebruarini (2015), showed that variable has a value of 0.144 products, have a positive effect but not significantly influence customers' decisions in choosing BMT Sahara Tulungagung.

Price variables in this study had a positive influence 0.889, not significant ($P > 0.05$) to the consumer's decision to choose the BMT in Kolaka. This is different from those reported by Pebruarini (2015), indicates that the variable price has a negative effect and no significant effect on the customer's decision. This is evidenced by the value of the regression coefficient -0.040 products.

Variable spot in this study had a positive effect of about 0.654 was significantly ($P < 0.05$) against the decision of consumers chose BMT in Kolaka. Pebruarini (2015), indicates that the variable places in BMT Tulungagung approximately 0.290 which is the highest score and have the greatest influence on the result of the significant value of the place is 0,008. Efendi and Utami (2016), Showed that travel time from home to the BMT had a negative effect and significant effect. Muljadi *et al.*, (2014) Showed that the sample of this research were 6 BMTs from each district and city in Banten Province have product, price, and people were still deviations from shariah concept, but the application for promotion and place were suitable with provisions of the shariah.

Related to the variable a customer's decision to choose BMT, different things reported by Wijayanti and Sumekar (2009), that only partially variable product, price, and promotion. While variable location significantly affect members in the

use of BMT Bina Ummah KJKS Sejahtra Lasem. It is also in line with the report Dianita (2015), that factor does not show the location and no significant positive influence on the decision of customers using the services of BMT El Shifa Ciganjur South Jakarta.

Conclusion

Concluded that factor marketing strategy of funding decision of customer choose BMT in Kolaka Regency :

- a. Community decision base on calculated rated R square of 0.975 or 95.7% strongly influenced by the factor have been determined, such as product, price, place, and promotion.
- b. Variable product, place and promotion significant affected to marketing strategy of funding decision of customer to choose BMT. However, variable price was not significantly.
- c. Variable promotion highly influenced factor of marketing strategy.

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